

Conference Abstract

Conservational rights and wrongs - protection of invasive populations of *Carassius carassius* and artificial habitats for repopulation of damaged native populations?

Ivana Buj[‡], Ivan Beno[‡], Nikola Renić[‡], Zoran Marčić[‡]

[‡] Faculty of Science University of Zagreb, Zagreb, Croatia

Corresponding author: Ivana Buj (ivana.buj@biol.pmf.hr)

Received: 17 Dec 2025 | Published: 30 Dec 2025

Citation: Buj I, Beno I, Renić N, Marčić Z (2025) Conservational rights and wrongs – protection of invasive populations of *Carassius carassius* and artificial habitats for repopulation of damaged native populations? ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e182752. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e182752>

Abstract

Similar to many other regions, crucian carp (*Carassius carassius* (Linnaeus, 1758)) is facing strong anthropogenic threats in Croatia, resulting in a reduction of its distribution range, local extinctions, lowering of its population abundances and diversities, presence of genetically contaminated populations and bringing several remaining populations on the verge of extinction. Despite the global IUCN assessment of this species as least concerned (LC) and its wide distribution range (throughout majority of Europe), scientists are expressing growing concerns that genetically pure and viable populations of crucian carp have become rare and that real distribution range, population sizes and their future prospects are much worse than currently presumed. Due to the lack of scientific investigation, the real status of this species in Croatian watersheds has not been described so far, nor have any conservation measures been designed, despite field observations indicating a strong reduction in distribution and abundances, and even local extinctions. Thereafter, for the first time, we have conducted comprehensive field investigation in order to check the presence of crucian carp populations on seemingly adequate localities, as well as localities that correspond with literature reports. We have employed molecular genetic analyses (based on mitochondrial and nuclear genetic

markers) in order to check whether the sampled populations are genetically pure or genetic contamination occurred (mostly due to hybridization with the prussian carp *Carassius gibelio* (Bloch, 1782). Furthermore, we have analyzed the genetic diversity of the sampled populations, their effective population sizes and gene flows among them. The obtained results corroborated a significant reduction in the native distribution range of the crucian carp in Croatia and its replacement with Prussian carp on majority of localities. Interestingly, crucian carp is present in many artificial habitats, but also on several water bodies in the Alpine region of Croatia, outside of its native distribution range, where this species can be considered invasive. Since a few remaining native populations have fragmented distribution, low population sizes and genetic diversities, we will discuss the importance of artificial habitats and non-native populations for assuring the survival of this rare and endangered species in Croatia, as well as possible conservation measures.

Keywords

Artificial habitats, *Carassius carassius*, genetic structure, native vs. introduced populations, population decline

Presenting author

Ivana Buj

Presented at

International Conference: "The Fish of Muddy Waters"

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.